

CARBON FARMING SCHEMES

ANALYSIS AND ONLINE MAP

INVENTORY

The Road4Schemes project has gathered an inventory containing 160 European carbon farming schemes.

EITHER...

Some of the identified schemes focus exclusively on carbon sequestration....

...OR

...other scheme designs support a wider number of ecosystem services

KEY OUTPUT

Interactive map showing carbon farming schemes per country

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SCHEMES

Status %

Measures %

Certification

Certification type %

Ecosystem Services

Scope of Action %

Payment Terms %

Payment Models %

Enhancing carbon sequestration in agricultural soils is crucial for mitigating climate change but many different carbon farming practices are applied throughout Europe. Their opportunities and barriers for designing successful result-based carbon farming schemes that also include additional ecosystem services have been exploited.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply.

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ scientists, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FUNDED PROJECT Road4Schemes

The aim is to assess strengths, weaknesses, and different perceptions of current strategies and schemes for carbon farming.

The overall objective of Road4Schemes is to improve the foundation for advancing carbon farming across Europe.

PROJECT COORDINATOR

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Fostering the uptake of climate-smart sustainable soil management practices

Mission SOIL: conserve soil organic carbon stocks

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL funded project:
ROAD4SCHEMES

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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